

Ecosystem stability using Open Schooling methodology

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E Korakaki¹, A Apostolakakis² and E Georgoulakis³

¹ Model High School of Heraklion, Greece

² 1st Vocational High School of Arkalochori, Greece

³ High School of Malia, Greece

E-mails: korakaki_elen@hotmail.com, abapo80@gmail.com,
emgeorgoulakis@yahoo.com

Abstract. In this paper we are presenting a teaching proposal that we developed and applied to Greek school students in the school years 2020 to 2023. In this project we use the open-ended teaching methodology in combination with the use of digital tools. The purpose is to teach the Scientific way of thinking. Specifically, we want our Secondary Education students to get into the philosophy that we must analyze some data, get information, process them, make a hypothesis and justify with arguments whether our hypothesis is correct. Students study four different animals that we want to reintroduce into a Greek ecosystem, specifically the Gypaetus barbatus, the Eurasian lynx, the Black Francolin and the Eurasian Beaver. At the end, after weighing all the data, they will come to a conclusion. That is if a specific animal can be introduced and what special features should this reintroduction have. From the evaluation of the results of this scenario, the positive results of the proposal emerge as a deep understanding of the ecosystem processes and at the same time we see an increased interest in Sciences, apart from the fact that there is a development of student's digital and social skills. This didactic proposal can be applied as is or adapted to primary and secondary school students and also to different types of ecosystems and other animals as well.

1. Introduction

Reintroduction of animals is a strategy used to restore populations of species that are extinct or threatened with extinction. This strategy is used to help restore ecological balance and preserve biodiversity. Protecting surviving examples of rare or threatened ecosystems is vital, but recreation or restoration of degraded systems may also boost resilience and further enhance ecosystem functioning [1]. Reintroducing animals can be a challenging and complex process and requires careful planning and management. Projects and research are found the world over, with concentrations in Europe, North America, and on tropical islands [2].

Both ecological restoration and reintroduction of animals face many challenges. These challenges include the need for long-term monitoring, the potential for unwanted consequences, and the social and economic costs of efforts. Another challenge is the need for cooperation that requires the involvement of many stakeholders, such as government agencies, non-governmental organizations, local communities and landowners [3,4]. Cooperation and coordination are necessary to ensure that recovery and reintroduction efforts are successful.

On the other hand, Open Schooling means partnerships bringing together students with teachers, scientists and professionals, family members and policymakers for solving significant real-life challenges that they care about, discuss innovations supported by scientific education, cocreate knowledge and do actions for local community development [5]. Open Schooling promotes quality education for students to develop skills for sustainable careers and the transition to digital and green innovation in the 21st century. It expands access to learning traditionally provided through formal education systems, but can also be provided through online and distance education.

Students want to know more about real problems in order to engage the world and develop their skills, by using the CARE-KNOW-DO methodology. The CARE-KNOW-DO framework has been proposed as a basis for operationalising an Open Schooling approach, by introducing real-life issues for students to discuss and address, supported by partnerships between schools, universities, and societal representatives. This framework looks at education from a wider perspective that includes the needs for society and care for individuals [6]. It enables schools to establish a flexible and engaging environment where students explore socio-scientific issues they care about, learn essential science curriculum, and take science-based actions [5].

2. Methodology

This teaching proposal is designed to be implemented in three teaching hours (approximately 135 minutes). Students are divided and collaborate in groups under the guidance of the teacher. The implementation can be carried out in the computer lab or in the classroom with the usage of permitted electronic devices (laptops, tablets etc.) with an internet connection.

2.1. 1st teaching hour

2.1.1. Introduction

Firstly, we introduce the students to the topic and make a connection with the previous lessons and their existing knowledge. We also announce the objectives of this lesson, which are: A) Learn about ecosystem stability and reintroduction of animals, B) Collaborate in teams and use the Scientific way of thinking and C) Acquire a responsible attitude regarding the reintroduction of animals into ecosystems.

2.1.2. CARE

In the first step, CARE, we involve the families and the STEM professionals. We present to the students the bios of the four animals recommended for reintroduction. The presentation is done by using a worksheet that has links with video, a scientific article, food web and a digital game. The students have to ask members of their family or others at home to take part in the discussion. Moreover, we can invite a STEM professional to talk about rewilding.

CONNECT **car@**

Lynx

Video: Eurasian Lynx, Description, Characteristics and Facts

- <http://bit.ly/3Xr6bQc>

Some more information:

- <https://rewilding europe.com/blog/the-lynx-lowdown-an-interview-with-david-hetherington/>

• bit.ly/3PtS6iX

hawk

fox

lynx

hare

mouse

squirrel

plants

Let's play:

- bit.ly/3qVB9DH
- <https://www.jigsawplanet.com/?rc=play&pid=26038e7ef0f1>

Figure 1. Worksheet for lynx

2.2. 2nd teaching hour

2.2.1. 1st activity

In this stage the students have already studied the necessary information and discussed it with their families. So, they work as a team and choose the animal that they want to be reintroduced.

Firstly, they vote in a Google Form and at the same time they watch the results.

Figure 2. Voting form and results

In addition, they justify their decision in a Padlet. Next, each group will present their decision and a plenary debate follows.

Figure 3. Padlet in which the students justify their choice

2.2.2. *KNOW*

There are six different stages: INTERPRET, CLASSIFY, ACTIVATE, PLAN, SOLVE, ANSWER and YOUR TURN.

In the first one, INTERPRET, the purpose is the students to make sense of the whole situation. We give each one an Apply Thinking Guide about Wolves rewilding. Also, we introduce Yellowstone Park and what happened to its wolves. We present to the class the food web and set the problem: “Can you explain the effects of reintroducing wolves?”. Moreover, we give the objectives for the activity. In the CLASSIFY stage, the goal is to decide what type of problem this is, and which key concept is needed to solve it. We discuss why they will need to use the concept of feeding relationships to solve the problem. In the ACTIVATE stage, the purpose is to bring their organized knowledge of the ideas and skills they will need into your working memory. Students complete a simple task to activate their knowledge of feeding relationships, and how to use food webs. They write down the feeding relationships shown in the food web on the Apply Thinking Guide. In the PLAN stage, the goal is to work out how they will solve the problem, step by step. We show them a plan for solving the problem. In the SOLVE stage, they use ideas and skills to work out the answer. They use slides which model how to solve the problem. In the stage ANSWER, the purpose is to write an answer, with explanation and justification if needed. In the last one, YOUR TURN stage, the purpose is for students to complete a similar problem independently and to be provided feedback.

2.2.3. *Self-assessment*

Students play a Kahoot game in groups. There are a series of multiple choice questions to self assess the understanding of the Ecosystem stability by using food webs.

Figure 4. Self assessment

2.3. *3rd teaching hour*

2.3.1. *Scientific way of thinking*

In this stage we remind/teach students the Scientific way of thinking, which they will use in the 2nd activity. The Scientific way of thinking (the Scientific Method) is the process of reviewing ideas using

science, observations, investigational processes, and testing them to gain knowledge. The goal is to make outcomes of knowledge that may be meaningful to science. The Scientific Method is how scientists and researchers apply their scientific thinking. The Scientific way of thinking has specific steps: A) Define a Question to Investigate. As scientists conduct their research, they make observations and collect data. B) Make Predictions. Based on their research and observations, scientists will often come up with a hypothesis. C) Collect Data. D) Analyze the Data and E) Come to Conclusions [7].

To understand even better the Scientific way of thinking, we present to the students the following example:

A) The Question: What will happen to Yellowstone National Park, when we reintroduce wolves?

Figure 5. Example of food web before the reintroduction of wolves in Yellowstone National Park

B) Predictions: Based on the food web, scientists predict that some organisms will be reduced and some organisms will be increased.

Figure 6. Example of food web after the reintroduction of wolves in Yellowstone National Park

C) Collect data: After the reintroduction of wolves, scientists collect data from Yellowstone. They observe the changes in populations from each organism and from the ecosystem overall.

D) Analyze data: Scientists analyze the data and find the correlations of these changes.

E) Come to conclusions: Scientists come to the conclusion that the reintroduction of wolves was beneficial for Yellowstone National Park. The number of deer decreased, but the number of other organisms increased and Yellowstone flourished even more [8].

2.3.2. 2nd activity

In this stage the students had already been taught the Scientific way of thinking. So, every team votes once again the contestant that wants to be reintroduced. Furthermore, they justify their decision in the Padlet. Finally, each group presents their decision and a plenary debate follows. In this stage there is additional discussion about possible changes in students' choices and the reasons that led them to change their minds.

2.3.3. DO

This is the last step, DO. Students have to plan and deliver a campaign to persuade an audience that an animal should be reintroduced. They do research and start the preparation of their presentation at home, with support from the family. At the school, they work with the Brainstorming method. The teacher gives an online concept map to fill in by using keywords to gather the positives of the rewilding of species in an ecosystem but from the point of view of ecology, agriculture, etc. of a

region. The students are also provided with examples of good practices that have been done in the context of this step. Moreover, we involve STEM professionals who act as an audience, review the quality of presentations, give feedback and be a judge.

Figure 7. Online concept map

2.3.4. Evaluation

The evaluation of the students takes place in two phases of the project, in the steps KNOW and DO, by using rubrics.

a. For the evaluation in the step KNOW:

The evaluation will be carried out after the students have done the five of the six different stages: INTERPRET, CLASSIFY, ACTIVATE, PLAN, SOLVE and ANSWER. So, they have already answered the question: “Can you explain the effects of reintroducing wolves?”. Moreover, they have applied their knowledge of feeding relationships and have learned the step-by-step process for solving problems by using an Apply Thinking Guide. Finally, they have to complete a similar problem independently.

Assessment rubric

Score	Level	Description	Typical student response
1	No link	One relevant idea	"I choose wolves. Wolves eat deer, so there will be less deer"
2	Partial link	> one relevant idea, simple connections	"I choose wolves. Wolves eat deer so there will be less deer and more plants."
3	Full link	At least two ideas logically connected. Use of some scientific language.	"I choose wolves. Wolves eat deer so the population of deer will decrease. Deer eat leaves, nuts, seeds, fruit and grasses so the population of plants will increase. This provides more plants for insects, finches and squirrels to eat so their population will increase"
4	Extended link	Several ideas connected with scientific reasoning. May link to other concepts. Use of accurate scientific language.	"I choose wolves. Wolves eat deer, so the population of deer will decrease. With less deer there will be more plants. With more plants, the population of the herbivores that eat plants (insects, finches and squirrels) will increase. A higher population of herbivores provides food for predators - bats, foxes and owls so their population will also increase. So, the introduction of wolves will result in the increase in population of lots of different animals at every stage of the food chain"

Figure 8. Assessment rubric for the step KNOW

For the evaluation in the step DO:

Students collect evidence for claims. We give them a sheet which describes how to plan their presentation by collecting evidence for four different claims. Next, they plan their presentation in their group and finally groups present their presentation. We use an assessment checklist.

Assessment checklist		SS5					
Section	Content	Group/ animal	Group/ animal	Group/ animal	Group/ animal	Group/ animal	Group/ animal
Beginning	Overview of what you will talk about						
	Information about rewilding						
Strongest claim	Stating the claim						
	Giving evidence that supports it						
	Giving reasons						
Other claim 1	Stating the claim						
	Giving evidence that supports it						
	Giving reasons						
Other claim 2	Stating the claim						
	Giving evidence that supports it						
	Giving reasons						
End	Repeating the strongest claim						
	Telling your audience what to do						
Total for presentation (mark out of 13)							

Figure 9. Assessment rubric for the step DO

3. Results

The goal of the teaching proposal was to combine the Scientific way of thinking with an educational practice that would arouse the interest of the students. That is, we wanted students to achieve a deeper understanding of scientific research in Sciences (analyze data, get information, process them, make a hypothesis and justify with arguments whether our hypothesis is correct), but in a more enjoyable process. For this purpose, we used the open-ended teaching methodology in combination with the use of digital tools.

To evaluate the proposal in terms of the achievement of its objectives, a graded criteria scale (Rubric) was used twice. The results were very encouraging.

Particularly, in the step KNOW the majority of students were able to do a full or extended link using at least two logically connected ideas. Moreover, some of them used several ideas connected with scientific reasoning. Also, many of them used accurate scientific language and they gave links to other concepts.

Furthermore, in the step DO their presentations include all required elements as well as additional information. Namely, they gave evidence with reasons to support their claim. There was the strongest claim for rewilding an animal and a brief description for at least two other claims.

Additionally, the students voted twice for the animal that they wanted to be reintroduced into the Greek ecosystem. Through the voting we wanted to record any changes in decision making after teaching the Scientific way of thinking. The first vote was after the step CARE. The participants had studied the bio of the animals and had discussed it with their families. The second one took place after the step KNOW. They had been taught the Scientific way of thinking and the Scientific data were added to the discussion after speaking with an expert scientist. Admittedly, a remarkable change was observed in the students' decisions. While in the first vote the majority of students chose the beaver for rewilding, in the second one no one chose the particular animal. Also, they justified their view on the fact that it would not have a chance of survival as there was no suitable ecosystem, so any rewilding attempt would face many problems. On the other hand, the majority in the second vote supported the rewilding of Gypaetus.

In addition, students evaluated this scenario using the online application of Mentimeter. This evaluation aimed to record the participants' attitude (positive - negative) towards the teaching proposal. All the students evaluated the proposal very positively. Also, they have to describe their feelings about the teaching method by using one word. They wrote the words: playful, enjoyable, interesting, knowledge, funny, team work.

4. Conclusions

For the best address of the rapid and constant technological, social, and economic change in society, formal education practices should be reinforced by non-formal educational practices. The Open Schooling satisfies this need, as schools are transformed from traditional educational institutions into community partnerships and become agents of community well-being [9].

In this project we use the open-ended teaching methodology in combination with the use of digital tools. From the evaluation of this scenario, the positive results of the proposal emerge as a deep understanding of the ecosystem processes and at the same time we see an increased interest in Sciences, apart from the fact that there is a development of students' digital and social skills. Also, with the use of digital tools, the educational process becomes playful and therefore more enjoyable for the students. Moreover, the collaboration with scientists and experts increased the students' interest in future professional employment in the STEM field.

Admittedly, this teaching proposal needs to be implemented in a larger number of schools so that there is more data and we can talk with certainty about the cultivation of the Scientific way of thinking of the participating students.

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